

Hierarchy of clumps fragments : a den for the formation of local star-clusters using a graph theory-based approach

Benjamin Thomasson,¹ Isabelle Joncour,¹ Estelle Moraux,¹ Frédérique Motte¹

¹ Institut de planétologie et d’astrophysique de Grenoble, University of Grenoble Alpes, France

Abstract

The spatial distribution of YSOs might give some clues on the fragmentation process of molecular clouds. Indeed, the small significant stellar structures (NESTs) discovered in Taurus (Joncour *et al.*, 2018) are interpreted as pristine imprints of star formation process and may be a consequence of the fragmentation of gaseous substructures. This work aims to investigate at which spatial scale gas clumps are fragmenting to form NESTs. We design a graph theory-based approach to characterise the properties of fragmentation and apply it to Herschel observations of NGC2264.

Using the *getsf* procedure (Men’shchikov, 2021), we extracted gas clumps catalogs at various scales. The observational data sets are taken from the Herschel’s five bands emission maps of NGC2264, covering scales from ~ 6 kAU to ~ 26 kAU. From those catalogs we build a directed graph in which the nodes are either associated to individual clump or YSO, and the oriented links between them define an inclusive relation between nodes.

Spatial distribution of multi-scale structures in NGC2264 reveals that hierarchical nested fragmentation is primarily observed in the high density central part of NGC2264 whereas monolithic collapse occurs in the sparser regions. Star formation may result from hierarchical fractal collapse of one massive dense clump (MDC), or a cluster of MDCs to form the stellar NESTs.

1 Introduction

Properties of local mini star-clusters (NESTs, Joncour *et al.*, 2018; González *et al.*, 2021) are suspected to hint pristine imprints of star formation process, and highlighted two regimes of cloud fragmentation. This work aims to check the existence of a hierarchical fragmentation cascade in the NGC2264 molecular cloud, and assess its statistical properties in a 5-30 kAU range scale. NGC2264 is a 723pc (Cantat-Gaudin *et al.*, 2018) distant cluster that is laying within the Monoceros OB1 East giant molecular cloud.

We investigate the fragmentation properties by performing a multi-scale analysis of the molecular cloud using a graph-theory based representation in order to connect the YSOs with their parental gas. Networks, and more specifically dendrograms, or trees, have already been used to study clouds hierarchy (Houllahan & Scalo, 1992; Rosolowsky *et al.*, 2008) by using successive iso-density contours on a single map. We propose here a new analysis which consists of extracting clumps independently on multiple column density maps of different spatial resolution. These clumps are then matched together following a parent/child inclusiveness principle, and a directed graph is built. The data are presented in Section 2 while Section 3 describes our analysis method. The results are given in Section 4 and are followed by a short discussion on the fragmentation properties in Section 5, and in Section 6 we conclude with a summary.

2 Data

To probe the 5-30 kAU range scale, we use the Herschel HOBYS multi-bands observation (Motte *et al.*, 2010) of NGC2264 which consists of 5 emission maps at [70, 160, 250, 350, 500] μ m with a respective resolution of [8.4, 13.5, 18.2,

24.9, 36.3]arcsec. From these 5 emission maps, column density maps at each resolution were computed and a source extraction was performed using *getsf* (Men’shchikov, 2021) to obtain 5 catalogs of clumps of [8.4, 13.5, 18.2, 24.9, 36.3]arcsec resolution (see more details for data processing in Thomasson *et al.* in prep). *A posteriori* selection is done on the 8.4" clumps by removing spurious sources defined as all the clumps without any counterpart at higher resolution. This selection is done specifically on these clumps because the 8.4" map is very noisy. In complement of those 5 catalogs of clumps, we use a catalog of class 0/I YSOs extracted from Spitzer survey (Rapson *et al.*, 2014). The final population we use is shown Table 1.

Table 1: Population of massive dense clumps (MDCs) and young stellar objects (YSOs) for each scale.

	YSOs	Total
MDCs	70 μ m	111
	130 μ m	93
	250 μ m	83
	350 μ m	70
	500 μ m	57
	Total	414
YSOs + MDCs		501

3 Methodology

The method presented here is a multi-scale spatial analysis of extended objects. The ellipsoidal clumps extent is defined at 2σ of their gaussian spatial emission profile, and the

YSOs are defined as circular object with radius of $2''$ (Spitzer's beam).

Because they originated from different resolution, some elements of the available catalogs can be spatially included one into another while other can be distant from one to another and distributed in the cloud. A common way to see these ellipsoidal clumps at different spatial scales is through a geometrical representation. However, it does not provide any information unless it can be directly seen by eye, and it become crowded when a lot of clumps are superimposed. Moreover, no statistics can be derived from such representation.

For that reason, we propose in this study a graph representation of the inclusiveness, where one node represents one element from the catalogs with its specific scale, whether it is a clump, or a YSO (see Figure 1). These nodes are linked together when their physical counterparts are included one into another. This link is directed from the node of higher scale to the node of lower scale such that the highest scales are considered as parents, and the lowest scales as children. We request a minimum area overlap between the clumps of 75% of the child area for the link to be made. As a result of this connection, clumps that are spatially correlated in the sense of inclusiveness, will naturally build disconnected sub-network. It means that, for a cloud or a sub-region of a cloud, each sub-network will represent a complex of clumps nested inside each other. Those complexes are designated as "structures", for which we give examples in Figure 2 with their geometrical counterparts. Each structure is described by its equivalent network, which will exhibit different features, such as nesting (see Section 5), depending on the way the nodes are connected to each other. Thus, 3 kind of structures are defined according to their number of final children (i.e the ending nodes of the directed network), which are designated as "fragments" :

1. the hierarchical structures, which contains at least 2 fragments ;
2. the linear structures, which contains only 1 fragment ;
3. the isolated structures, which are isolated nodes (no edges)

Figure 1: Construction of the network. One element, whether it is MDC or YSO is represented as a node. The scales are indicated by colors, and a link is created when the area of a child is 75% inside its parent. The network is directed from higher scales to lower scales.

4 Results in NGC2264

4.1 Location of hierarchical structures

The class 0/I YSOs are found to be mainly nested in the central part of the cloud, where a high concentration of hierarchical structures are located. This region of NGC2264 is

Figure 2: Equivalence between geometrical representation (up), and network representation (down) of 3 examples of structures we define. We choose to show a tree representation to lighten the network. The actual network is composed by all the edges between any two nested objects such that multiple paths can exist between two nodes.

the densest of the cloud and constitutes a hub for the northern et southern filaments as seen in Figure 3. Linear structures seems to dominate in these filaments and can contain a single YSO. In NGC2264 map, we have the information of the structures location, but we do not clearly know how the nodes of the structures are organized with their relatives. In Figure 4, we propose a network representation of the multi-scale arrangement of clumps and YSOs. In such a representation, the hierarchical structures that settle in the central part of NGC2264 have more condensed edges showing that they tend to fragment more than in other regions, and they fragment into more than one piece.

Figure 3: NGC2264 high resolution density map at $18''$ (Nony *et al.*, 2021) overlapped with structures extent. 5 regions visually discriminated to distinguish North and South filament, the two dense regions in the central hub and eastern region.

Figure 4: Network representation of NGC2264 structures. Each MDC and YSO is represented as a node with respect to their specific scale, given by a ring. Inner rings represent the higher scales and the scale is decreasing towards the outer rings. The angular position gives the membership of a structure to a specific region defined in Figure 3. Hierarchical structures are represented in blue, linear structures are in red and isolated (singleton) are in black. Parts of the cloud that are not covered by any existing region is labelled "outskirt". All the regions are separated by dotted lines.

4.2 Modes of fragmentation

Even if hierarchical structures represent a small fraction of the whole population extracted ($\sim 10\%$), they contain 40% of the total clumps, and 62% of the total YSOs, as it can be seen in Figure 5. This is compatible with the previous result that shows high density of edges in these structures. Thus, we can establish that there is two dominant modes of fragmentation concerning more than 80% of the whole population of clumps and YSOs of the cloud: the hierarchical and the linear modes. The hierarchical one is interpreted as being related to hierarchical fragmentation, where a clump collapses and fragments into multiple seeds of star forming regions. The linear one is interpreted as being related to monolithic fragmentation, where the physical conditions support a simple gravitational collapse, that ends up on only one fragment created in the structure (see Joncour this conference).

4.3 Breeding of YSOs

Hierarchical structures in NGC2264-D, located in the northern region of the central hub, contain more fragments (36 YSOs and 13 clumps) and produces more YSOs than NGC2264-C (13 YSOs and 12 clumps). Thus, NGC2264-D's hierarchical structures appear more YSO-fertile. Moreover, NGC2264-D's hierarchical structures produce on average 4.5 YSOs for each of its parental clump, while NGC2264-C produces 3.2 YSOs for each of its parental clump. When comparing the efficiency of YSOs production between hierarchical mode and monolithic mode in the whole cloud, we found that on average, hierarchical fragmentation produces 3.4 YSOs/structure, while the monolithic mode produces 0.2 YSOs/structure on average. Monolithic fragmentation does not seem to be efficient since we would expect a maximum

Figure 5: Total population proportion of structures (*top*) and of YSOs or MDCs in structures (*bottom*).

of 1 YSO/structure, and this particular mode does not explain the presence of stellar groups (NESTs, Joncour *et al.*, 2018; González *et al.*, 2021) one can observe, for example in Taurus, as well as in 39 other star forming region (see Gonzalez this conference). Therefore, we can legitimately think that star formation process is mainly driven by hierarchical processes rather than monolithic processes.

5 Fractal property of the gas fragmentation

The density of edges we can see in Figure 4 is related with what we call the nesting, which describes how many nested children fragments are contained inside parental fragments for a given structure. To quantify this feature, we define a nesting coefficient \mathcal{N} , which consists of computing the number of weighted triangles in a structure (see Figure 6).

This number of weighted triangles is normalized such that if $\mathcal{N} \in \mathbb{N}$ the process of fragmentation is close to a fractal fragmentation process of index \mathcal{N} , meaning that each fragment is split into \mathcal{N} pieces and so on. The weight of the edges is taken as the scaling ratio between two nodes (from higher scale to lower). A detailed description of this coefficient will be given in Thomasson *et al.*, in prep. The nesting coefficient mean value of the hierarchical structures population is ~ 1.4 . For an ideal binary fractal distribution, we would expect $\mathcal{N} = 2$. It means that hierarchical structures, that have to fragment into multiple pieces, does not fragment at all scales: inside a same structure, there are scales where one parent delivers one child, and other scales where one parent delivers multiple children.

Figure 6: Example of triangles in a graph. (left) Nested structure with 3 scales and 2 nodes appearing at each of the 2 sub-scales, that is forming 4 distinct triangles. (right) Separated structure that only possesses 2 scales which is insufficient to define a triangle and therefore, a nesting coefficient.

6 Conclusion

We propose a multi-scale description of fragmentation using Herschel’s survey of NGC2264, allowing us to probe a 5-30kAU range scale. Massive dense clumps (MDCs) at [8.4, 13.5, 18.2, 24.9, 36.3]arcsec resolution were extracted independently in 5 different density maps using *getsf* algorithm (Men’shchikov, 2021). Along with class 0/I YSOs (Rapson *et al.*, 2014), we build a directed network with nodes that represent either MDCs or YSOs, between which an oriented link from the higher scale to the lower scale is defined under the condition of inclusiveness.

The analysis of the multiplicity of fragments in the disconnected sub-networks enlighten 2 main modes of fragmentation : hierarchical fragmentation ($\sim 40\%$ of the total elements), which we associated to hierarchical collapse of the gas, and linear fragmentation ($\sim 50\%$ of the total elements), which we associated to monolithic collapse. The main results are summarized as follow :

- Hierarchical fragmentation is the most efficient mode of fragmentation to produce YSOs (3.4 fragments/structure on average) compared to the linear one (0.2 fragments/structure)
- Hierarchical fragmentation is dominant in the most massive region of NGC2264 which is the central hub while linear structures are mainly extracted in lower dense part of the cloud
- The analysis of network representing the hierarchical structures hinted that fragmentation does not always occur at all scales, which could explain a low value of the nesting coefficient (~ 1.4)

Other indicators can be used to describe the fragmentation of hierarchical structures, such as the production of fragment at each scale, the degree distribution of networks, or the proportion of YSOs associated with gaseous binary (Thomasson in prep).

This methodology needs to be fully tested in numerical simulations in order to compare the result of the spatial fragmentation we obtain. We will also apply the same methodology in numerical simulations following the evolutionary state of clumps with time, and have access to the dynamic of fragmentation. We also intend to probe deeper scales, lower than 5kAU, such that we would be able to assess the fragmentation properties on the very close environment of YSOs. We

expect that the hierarchical fragmentation will continue at lower scale to form wide multiple stellar systems (Joncour *et al.*, 2017).

Acknowledgments

This work was founded by the Ecole Doctorale de Physique of the University of Grenoble-Alpes. I would like to acknowledge Alexander Men’shchikov (CEA Paris Saclay) for providing us with catalogs of MDCs, as well as Thomas Nony (UNAM) for his help, and who let us use his high resolution column density map of NGC2264.

References

- Cantat-Gaudin, T., Jordi, C., Vallenari, A., Bragaglia, A., Balaguer-Núñez, L., *et al.* 2018, *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 618, A93. Publisher: EDP Sciences.
- González, M., Joncour, I., Buckner, A. S. M., Khorrami, Z., Moraux, E., *et al.* 2021, *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 647, A14.
- Houllahan, P. & Scalzo, J. 1992, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 393, 172.
- Joncour, I., Duchêne, G., & Moraux, E. 2017, *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 599, A14.
- Joncour, I., Duchêne, G., Moraux, E., & Motte, F. 2018, *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 620, A27.
- Men’shchikov, A. 2021, arXiv:2102.11565 [astro-ph]. ArXiv: 2102.11565.
- Motte, F., Zavagno, A., Bontemps, S., Schneider, N., Henneemann, M., *et al.* 2010, *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 518, L77.
- Nony, T., Robitaille, J.-F., Motte, F., Gonzalez, M., Joncour, I., *et al.* 2021, *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 645, A94.
- Rapson, V. A., Pipher, J. L., Gutermuth, R. A., Megeath, S. T., Allen, T. S., *et al.* 2014, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 794, 124. ArXiv: 1409.1131.
- Rosolowsky, E. W., Pineda, J. E., Kauffmann, J., & Goodman, A. A. 2008, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 679, 1338. Publisher: IOP Publishing.